

Quantum gravity model based on spherical field

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Abstract

I have established a quantum gravity model with spherical field as the core carrier of the theory. It can explain gravity from microscopic to macroscopic. The establishment of this model requires a precondition, which is a law I gave: density reaction law and its inference. At present, this model has completed the concept proposal, logical deduction and self-consistency verification. The mathematical tool part has not yet been completed.

Introduction

As we all know, the goal of quantum gravity theory is to give a holistic explanation of gravity at both microscopic and macroscopic scales. Therefore, a complete quantum gravity theory must include both "big" and "small" features. Currently, the most competitive candidate theories of quantum gravity are string theory and loop quantum theory. The problem with these theories is that they start from a single point of view and only consider problems from a microscopic perspective. If a theory can "simultaneously" start from both microscopic and macroscopic perspectives, the effect may be better and the theory may be more natural. This is exactly my goal.

Model establishment

Basic assumptions:

1 Carrier:

A suitable carrier is one of the most basic elements of the theory. Just like the "string" of string theory and the "loop" of loop quantum theory. In quantum gravity theory, this carrier must meet some restrictive requirements as much as possible: large and small, concrete, and spread throughout the universe. Candidate list: force, energy, matter, time, space, field, wave, particle. The selection process is as follows: waves and particles can be described by fields; space and time themselves are the objects to be explained by quantum gravity theory; force, energy and matter are more inclined to describe physical phenomena rather than specific physical entities. Winner: field.

2 Field properties:

Gravitational fields generally have the following characteristics: spherical distribution, the highest density at the core, the density is negatively correlated with the radius, the radius is infinite, and the density of the field is positively correlated with gravity. Therefore, spherical fields also have these characteristics. Figure 1

Figure 1. Field

3 Particles:

Particles are the high-density parts of the core area of spherical fields, or in other words, the core part of spherical fields is expressed as particles. Figure 2

Figure 2. Particle

4 Gravity:

Gravity is generated by the interaction between two spherical fields. This interaction is set as a trend of diffusion from high density to low density.

5 Density reaction law and inference:

Density reaction law: Any reaction or interaction causes the overall density of the system to decrease.

Inference: Any reaction has a density threshold for the reaction to occur. When the density is lower than the threshold, the reaction does not occur.

The density reaction law and inference are derived by induction, based on a series of reactions and interactions including the Big Bang model.

Explanation of gravity:

Use spherical fields to explain the gravity between two "particles". When two particles are at a certain distance, the gravity between them is divided into three parts: inner section, middle section, and outer section.

Inner section:

This part of gravity is provided by the core of the spherical field. The size of this area is extremely small and the density is extremely high. Therefore, this area can be approximately regarded as a point gravity source and calculated using Newton's law. Figure 3

Figure 3. Gravity in the inner section

Middle section:

This part is located outside the inner section and covers an appropriate range. Based on the structural characteristics of the spherical field, the middle section gravity expresses an approximate "asymptotic freedom" feature, that is, gravity is positively correlated with the radius. Figure 4

Figure 4. Gravity in the middle section

Outer section:

This part is located outside the middle section, extending to infinity. Due to the huge size of this part of the spherical field, the particles are approximately located at the center of the spherical field, and the gravitational forces in all directions cancel each other out, and the net gravitational force tends to zero. Figure 5

Figure 5. Gravity in the outer section

Model application:

1 The setting of a spherical field actually does one thing: replacing the probability distribution of the wave function with a density distribution.

2 Spherical field explanation of wave function collapse:

The field is observed in particle state. Reason: Observation is usually based on reaction (interaction), and the reaction has a density threshold. Part of the field density reaches the threshold and participates in the reaction. This part of the field is observed in particle state. The rest of the field fails to reach the threshold, so it does not participate in the reaction and is not observed. Therefore, the field has not collapsed, but most of the field does not participate in the observed reaction.

3 Spherical field explanation of wave-particle duality:

- (1) The spherical field is a field, and the field naturally has wave properties.
- (2) The field can be expressed as a particle state, see the explanation of wave function collapse.

4 Spherical field explanation of double-slit interference experiment:

- (1) The spherical field is a field with wave properties, so it can interfere with itself.
- (2) The self-interference state of the spherical field can be destroyed. If the observation method reaches a certain threshold, it can trigger a related reaction and break the self-interference state.

5 Spherical field explanation of quantum entanglement:

Since the radius of the spherical field is infinite, the two entangled quanta actually overlap each other. This correlation state can be roughly regarded as two gears meshing with each other, so it is natural for them to have some kind of correlation interaction. The same principle can explain the entanglement of multiple quanta and the fragility of quantum entanglement. Figure 6

Figure 6. Quantum Entanglement

6 Spherical field explanation of Pauli's exclusion principle:

Essentially, the Pauli exclusion principle and quantum entanglement are the same thing. Therefore, there must be some kind of "coordinated" interaction between the two quanta so that they can coexist in the same orbit. Otherwise, they will repel each other and generate repulsive force. Figure 7

Figure 7. Pauli's exclusion principle

7 Spherical field explanation of dark energy:

The Pauli exclusion principle indicates that there is repulsion between particles, and the fragility of quantum entanglement indicates that the amount of this repulsion is huge. Obviously, there is both gravity and repulsion between particles. There is a superposition field of gravity and repulsion between particles. Moreover, the range of action of this superposition field is infinite. The intensity of the field is positively correlated with the density, and the intensity of the field is extremely low in places with extremely low density. Therefore, there is reason to believe that there is such a possibility: when the density is below a certain threshold, the repulsion is slightly stronger than the gravity, and the superposition field expresses repulsion. Figure 8

Figure 8. Superposed field

Astronomical observations show that the expansion of the universe first slows down and then accelerates. The superposition field can explain this phenomenon: in the early stage of the expansion of the universe, the density of the universe is higher than a certain threshold, the superposition field expresses gravity, and the universe at this time is decelerating expansion. Later, as the universe continued to expand, the density in some places was lower than the threshold, and the superposition field expressed repulsion. As a result, the expansion of the universe began to gradually accelerate, resulting in more places with density below the threshold, and the expansion of the universe further accelerated.

Therefore, the essence of dark energy is: in a spherical field system, the superposition field between particles expresses repulsion where the density is below the threshold, and the expansion of the universe further reduces the density, resulting in more repulsion expression, which drives the universe to further accelerate expansion. Figure 9

Figure 9. The universe changes from decelerating expansion to accelerating expansion

8 Spherical field explanation of dark matter:

The dark matter effect of galaxies can be explained by "mid-segment gravity". By the same token, the dark matter effect in the solar system can be explained by "inner segment gravity". Therefore, the essence of dark matter is: in a spherical field system, gravity is expressed in the middle segment, and at this time gravity is positively correlated with distance.

9 Spherical field explanation of particle mass distribution:

The mass of elementary particles is not concentrated at one point, but distributed in the form of a spherical field.

Discussion

The spherical field model actually confirms that the basic structure of the world is the spherical field, which can describe gravity at various scales. It indicates that gravity is generated based on matter itself, not on space. So, relativity may be an equivalent expression rather than an essence. In addition, the composition of matter is not only through combination, but also through superposition. The spherical field model expresses a certain degree of consistency with existing theories and explains some experimental results. This gives the spherical field model more possibilities. However, the mathematical model of the spherical field model has not been completed, and the establishment of the mathematical model will be a very difficult and time-consuming task. This requires the participation of everyone.